
Experiential Input by Psychiatric Professionals and Mental Health Patients towards Patient's Good Healthy Wellbeing and Normalization

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ABSTRACT

Good mental wellbeing is of utmost importance to all psychiatric doctors, nurses, clinical psychologists, social workers, police officers, prison officers, occupational therapist, family, government, friends and the patients himself/herself. Being able to coordinate all the sense organs and put it to good use is very necessary as one tries on daily basis to meet all the basic physiological needs. And by that one can cater for him/herself, family, friends and others. Any one lacking this ability and opportunity can be classified to be a mentally ill person or individual. This investigation or research hence sorts to investigate how good healthy wellbeing can be obtained or generated from a mentally retarded person. With solutions, methods and procedures based on the experience from both the health workers in the treatment process and the patient or the experience of the mentally ill person. Recovering from a mentally challenged world to a healthy world of individuals should be done on the basis of stakeholder participation. It is either achieved in the positive direction or in the negative direction. The positive direction is towards obtaining a healthy wellbeing willing to impact on the family, community, country or world positively. The negative impacts is towards shaking of hands and legs, crippling, madness or completely unto death. In all these scenarios, the experiential workers and patients have to play effective roles towards attainment of needed outputs of a healthy being towards advancement of country Ghana or the world in general.

Keywords: Psychiatrist, psychologist, physiological, mental, patient, normalization, clinical, healthy, neurological, treatment.

1 INTRODUCTION

No one wants to be tagged or teased in the name of mentally retarded or ill person. Because of the word stigmatization. Mentally ill individuals are stigmatized on daily basis because of a mental condition or for being exposed to a psychiatric department, home or ward for treatment. Mentally ill patients are subjected or exposed to all kinds of treatments processes with the ultimate aim of bringing the person back to normalcy. Bringing the person back to normalcy is the process of treating a mentally ill person to a state of state/community/country/personal acceptance. In such a process, all kinds of people plays

various roles to achieve the needed output or results. The group making up the treatment process and playing various roles includes the psychiatric doctor and nurse, clinical psychologist, social worker, occupational therapist, police officer, prison officer, friends, colleague workers, government and the patient him/herself. But in all these classifications is re – classified into two main streams. *The experiential worker and experiential patient*. This two groups forms the major contributors towards the final wellbeing and good health of the patient. If there is no coordination or cooperation, there is an aspect of lies or break in chain or communication at any point in time between the experiential worker and experiential patient? Then the patients wellbeing or good healthy wellbeing attainment will be at risk. Another problem associated with good health wellbeing attainment can also be on the part of the experiential patient. Where the patient does not comply with or accepts the treatment process or procedures. But not withstanding, the patients justification and acceptance ability should be in favor or against all odds. Where the justification should be based on what he/she does, what he/she can do and what he/she is doing. In such a case, experiential reference should be from all the angles for final justification and discharge from the mental home or psychiatric hospital.

The brain is the master control room of every individual where it coordinates all the affairs of the human body on daily basis. Once there is hinderance in the effective coordination of the body by the brain, final results may be a mentally ill person. If a problem arises in any of the three brain segments: cerebrum, cerebellum and the medulla oblongata, one should expect drastic brain and body dysfunction in every regard. One cannot obtain 100% brain functionality but rather, expect some degree or percentage functionality at any point in time. But to a certain lower degree/percentage is classified as mentally ill or mentally retarded person or individual. If such a mental ill state or being is obtained, then it calls for psychiatric health professionals coordination and cooperation on such an individual to bring him/her to an acceptable state within the community or country. The experience of the psychiatric or health professional and the experience of the patient (mentally ill person) should play the greatest roles in the recreation or healing process of obtaining a new being or person. This new being or person should be adequately functional in terms of motive, behaviour, attitude, conformity and thinking when it comes to social vices, rules and regulations within the society. Such new creation or being will then be able to play major roles in the family or community or country. The process is very long excepts one obtained in terms of genetic mutations or genetically obtained mentally retarded person.

Mentally retarded person/individuals end up in the psychiatric homes from various backgrounds. Some of the contingencies that lands people in the mental homes includes failed marriages, taking in psychoactives, collaspsing (where the brain is severely affected), spiritual attacks, failed examinations, occultisms, broken homes, failed businesses, flooding, natural disasters, injections gone wrong, old age treatments, deportations, stress, depressions, money rituals, road accidents and so on. To bring an individual in such a situation or state to a point of good healthy wellbeing or mental state requires tedious work. To obtain a state of normalcy for the affected person depends on hardwork on the part of experiential worker and experiential patients. This has become very necessary hence

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the need for each professional or individual involved in the healing process to play his/her undoubted role for about 85% to 92% healing.

2 REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS

2.1 Mental Home Establishment

Establishing institutions in Africa that reflected their own policies has been done since colonial authorities and over 100 years ago (Barbato et al., 2010). For west Africa alone, asylums were established between 1903 and 1908 in Calabar, Lagos and Accra (Sadowsky, 1999). Africa has a lot of ancient traditional systemes, orthodox healers and functional ways of working on social consequences of mental disorders within their communities or country. The set for stage for a major revolution in been able to provide effective treatment for severe mental disorders was after the first marketing of chlorpromazine, an anti-psychotic medication (Barbato et al., 2010). This resulted in the development of pharmaceutical agents that could effectively alleviate symptoms of a wide range of disorders. Only 30% of African countries have legislation (Eaton, 2010) that was developed since the 1990 (Barbato et al., 2010; WHO, 2005). This was after legislation quickly gotten out of date. Currently most mental illness treatments are limited to big hospitals in the African countries.

Global burden of disease study published in 1996 (Murray, 1990) used new ways of measuring health needs that incoorpeated measures of disability more than mortality (Barbato et al., 2010). Modern mental health issues and problems is vastly under resourced comparable to the burden they cause to families and communities. The 2001 (WHO) world Health Report New Understanding, New Hope also highlights the degree to which mental health needs was unmet globally, but most needs made the point that we now have good tool with which to address the needs (WHO, 2001; Eaton, 2010).

2.2 Mental Health and Wellbeing

Mental health is very important to the patient personally, towards the wellbeing of oneself, families, relations, country for a successful building of society and community. The WHO objective for mental health is to eleminate the burden of mental disorders worldwide (Barbato et al., 2010). Mental, neurological and substance use (psychoactives) are some of the major contributing factors towards mental instabilities and premature mortality and morbidity. The stigmatization surrounding mental health and human rights violation directed towards people with mental health issues compounds the problem of mental instability. As well as hindering people progress, generating a group of dependence attitudes with hindering efforts to rise out of poverty (Barbato et al., 2010). 14% of the global burden on individuals and country can be attributed to mental, neurological and substance abuse disorders (Sexena, 2010). About 30% of all the noncommunicable disease is due to these mental, neurological and substance use disorders. These burdens should be tackled collaboratively and through stakeholder participation. But all boils down to availability of mental treatment medicines and resources to help mental disorders individuals. The resources provided to tackle the huge burden of mental, neurological and

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substance use disorders have been inadequate to address these predicaments. About $\frac{1}{3}$ of the world countries do not have adequate budget to address mental health problems and hence becoming a burden to psychiatric professionals in such countries. There is also inefficiency in the use of the scarce and inadequate resources when it comes to usage and distribution of drugs and the resources involved in treatments (Saxena, 2010) in individual hospitals in a country. In most cases, patients and family have to bear the cost of treatments of the mentally incapacitated person. For example, many middle – income countries that have made substantial investments in large mental hospitals are reluctant to replace them with community – based and inpatient facilities in general hospitals, despite evidence that mental hospitals provide inadequate care and that community based services are more effective (Barbato et al., 2010; Saxena, 2010)

2.3 Diagnosis, Treatment, Recovery and Psychological Rehabilitation

Recovery as a process or method is a journey of personal growth and transformation. It involves the process of voicing out the signs and symptoms of the mental illness, diagnosis, prescription and final treatment. It is about moving beyond the diagnosis stage (Barbato et al., 2010; Redtke, 2010). Recovery also involves the process of creating a satisfying life of your choice. In the case of experiential in terms of the psychiatric professional and patient, then it should involve collaborative way of treatment in order to achieve needed results. Recovery is an empowering model for users (experiential patient) and those involved with the treatment (experiential professionals and cohorts). It stresses on the need for experiential patient strength, intelligence and ability to live a life fully satisfying and worth sharing the experience with others (Barbato et al., 2010). Recovery doesn't imply freedom from all signs and symptoms associated with mental health problems even though, individuals with psychosocial abilities may achieve recovery. It is worth noting that, some learn to live very well with a mental disorder in the family or society. Recovery views mental health interventions as tools for people to be able to live very well within the society and among people with the emphasis on the importance of choice. This is usually obtained or attained through collaborative work by both experiential workers and experiential patients. It is worth for the patient to play their collaborative role in the healing process for their complete good healthy wellbeing. This is because, they are the ones experiencing the symptoms, taking the injections, taking the drugs, going through the stigmatizations and experiencing all kinds of issues pertaining to human rights, abuses and choices in life. In most cases, mental disorders interventions comprises of a combination of medical, psychological and social interventions that take into accounts the living conditions of the individual and his/her wider community (Barbato et al., 2010).

2.4 Patients mental Health interventions

Patients or individuals with severe mental illness are worth identifying as some can be very dangerous in the society. This is especially in the case of those who takes Psychoactives in the community or society. Up to about 3500 home visits in India have taken place. Alternatively, individuals diagnosed with mental health issues comes with their relatives for

treatment (Christina, 2010; Barbato et al., 2010). Individuals are more accepting therapy following home visits as compared to group programmes as a study in India declares. After 900 consultation have been carried out, individuals including children with psychosis, mood disorders, epilepsy and common mental disorders have been seen (Christina, 2010; Barbato et al., 2010). Patients with multiple (different kinds of) disabilities or disorders may be assessed in the house or at the home. But this is usually the case in the western world. In cases of home treatments, diagnosis and needs assessment of the patient by the psychiatric doctor or nurse is done in the presence of the community level worker where appropriate. And this community level worker takes over especially in the case of the community level mental health treatment (Christina, 2010; Barbato et al., 2010). The mental health patient needs support, compliance when it comes to drugs intakes and injections, continued assessment of needs and assistance in varied ways in terms of medications. And in a case where the patient is not at the mental home, such assistance can be given by the community health worker. Since appropriate special techniques are used for special needs populations such as children (Christina, 2010; Barbato et al., 2010). This is not the case in Ghana where almost all mental homes are regionally situated or bound. In India, cases that are deemed complicated – having suicidal risks or disorganized behaviour are usually referred to the main hospitals for short term care (Christina, 2010; Barbato et al., 2010).

2.5 Experiential Psychiatric Professional

Experiential learning by psychiatrist and nurses is the act of learning everything about psychiatry and doing or performing all the activities and processes involved. It involves two things; just to act or to notice how we or one acts in the mental home or hospital (Burnard, 1996). Vicarious learning is learning from some of our mistakes or from the mistakes of others. All health professionals learn through reflecting on their practice. Experiential learning does not occur when we do not reflect on our practices. Reflecting on once practices, remembering and inferring on the past behaviors, actions and inactions that resulted in a positive or negative results; gave a life or resulted in death or madness in the process of mental healing. The issue of reflecting is crucial one. We must learn to remember ourselves (Burnard, 1996). Ouspensky (1988) argues that if we do not remember ourselves and notice what is happening as a psychiatrist or nurse, one will never be able to commit to memory the events or happenings that are taking place within and around us.

Psychiatrist and nurses attending to the wellbeing and welfare of mental ill patients need to learn and cultivate an increasing awareness of the senses, their changes through feelings and actions about the patients. A reflecting ability can help the experiential professional, psychiatrist, nurse or health professional in;

- Learning through talking care of the mental ill patients
- Working or walking in the field with the mentally challenged person.

2.6 Experiential Patient

Most experiential psychiatric patients are learning as they go through the process of psychiatric healing towards attainment of a healthy wellbeing and normalization in the society. In such a situation as the patient takes the drugs, gets the injection, goes for counselling on sleeping habits and changes, looks at the effects and impacts of drugs on oneself, he/she picks life changing and intelligent keys that will result in his/her total healing. The most obvious important methods of monitoring progress in experiential patient's life is by practicing the skills involved, and noticing the changes and development actions (Burnard, 1996). The practice aspect comes with going through the process of treatment. Whether going through harshly or gently. There is the need to be learning and trying new behaviors as the psychiatrist who is diagnosing and prescribing on weekly or monthly basis on signs and symptoms basis to expedite the healing process. Most drugs are added based on healing process and progressive signs as well as patient's adaptability. Such new drugs and methods are meant for the success of the journey and towards obtaining a new healthy wellbeing beneficial to family, community and country. It has to be noted that the decision to try out new methods and strategies towards helping the psychiatrist to obtain a healthy mental being ought to be conscious one. One should be able to remember the whole journey or process towards healing (Burnard, 1996). It is very easy to go through the process of mental healing or counselling skills and to believe that a lot has been gained from it. The truth is of course a lot will only be gained or achieved if the learning gained in it is transferred to the real situation. That is embarking on a hands – on procedural work done or practice of that activity.

3 METHODOLOGY

The method employed for this research work is the Patient and Psychiatrist Professional Experiential Method (PPPEM). In this research, the patient is seen as the mentally challenged person and works with the psychiatric professional for over a decade on various psychiatric problems or issues. The patient undergoes real time healing and simulation process all with the aim of achieving total healing for a mentally challenged person or individual. Three mental homes; mental department – Koforidua Regional Hospital – Mental department, Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital at Kumasi and Mental department, Pantang Hospital at Accra are the hospitals used to undertake this research work and study. The study involved taking and intelligent consultation with psychiatric doctors, nurses and health professionals. The research also entails reviewing literature and psychiatric readable materials to assess and review some reasons and essence of mental homes treatment in Ghana. **Fig 1.** below gives a diagrammatic illustration of the employed method for the research.

Fig 1: Methodological illustration of the employed method

4 OUTPUT AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Positive Experiential Impacts

4.1.1 Recovery Rate

Mental health problems and issues is a process and goes for some duration in the life of an individual. Recovery can be attained in the positive direction. In such a situation, a healthy complete wellbeing can be obtained but not in totality (100%) in mindset and behaviour. Even in terms of normal human beings, obtaining an individual with brain, mindset and motive of 100% in actions and inactions is impossible. Positive recovery is always in terms of an individual fit in attitude, motive, behaviour, imagination, thinking and ability for the welfare and advancement of oneself and society. Both the psychiatric doctors, nurses and health professionals, family members, community leaders all play major roles towards good healthy wellbeing attainment in all mental homes in Ghana and worldwide. Recovery becomes a problem on the part of the experiential patient when there is conflict of interest. No cooperation and collaboration on issues and healing process. Where one group may say he/she is ok when another school of thought says, he/she isn't well healed. When an individual falls into such a pit and recovers. Everyone expects no misunderstanding or any unfortunate accidents. This isn't possible as we continue to live in an institution or animal kingdom. If it becomes a continuous misunderstanding thing, that is when it becomes problematic but even that, it is worth looking deeper and closer as it can be out of scenarios generations. People may want such a person by doing menial jobs and wants the person by hook or crook means to end up in the mental home simply because of an associated depreciating factor. This is especially in the case of spiritual attacks (propagating good) or Occultic money making treasure adventures as monitored by Danquah (2023).

4.1.2 Experiential Patients Impacts towards healing

Mental health problems, associated stigmatization and infringing on once human rights and principles isn't pleasing at all. To me as an author and researcher, the most worrying mental health problems should be the once genetically generated. But the once out of social vices or issues, treasure hunting or those originating from issues of life should be treated with much respect as there exist the possibility of healing after continuous hard work on the patient. Danquah (2023) elaborates on the different categories of people and how they end up in mental homes. So in a way, the patient should and play major roles in the healing process of the mental health problem. But ought to fight through the process. When old cells/skin have to die or get removed from the body, new cells/skin have to evolve or grow. Mental health problems are always experienced after some age period or group if not genetically acquired.

I strongly believe it's usually out of creation from a world where the person is recreated and becomes a new being with the head and brain of a child. Such a person may need to go through the process of growth which is usually experienced at infancy. In going through the process may be all kinds of agitations, troubling's, misunderstandings and behaviors comparably to kid's world or associated with infants. But after some time may be the resultant adulthood attainment in the creation and process of healings. But this is usually regarded as mental illness (on the part of some people and need not be usually the case or all the cases) or mental challenges because of the associated wealth and money when such a scenario is generated from an occultic world for instance.

4.1.3 Experiential Psychiatrist Impacts

The experiences from psychiatric doctors, nurses, social workers and all associated with healings and the wellbeing of the mentally challenged individual is very important towards attainment or normalcy of such an individual. Whiles the psychiatric doctor and nurses are involved with the reading of signs and symptoms, diagnosis, prescription and administering of drugs, the psychologist, social worker, family, community and religious leaders and dieticians should play their roles of counselling and recommendation of appropriate food to facilitate the healing process of the mentally challenged person or individual. Even though the psychiatrist or nurse is involved with drugs issues in the healing process, he/she gets involved with all kinds of counselling issues and procedures. The family or immediate person to the mentally challenged person followed by the psychiatric doctor forms major players in the healing process also. There is the need for psychiatrist to counsel, advice, suggest to family members of weaning the mentally challenged person off drugs for close monitoring and assessment towards complete normalization. One ought to know that all the drugs are brain enhancements or constrains hence the possibility of a positive or negative repercussions at any point in time. If not weaning off completely or reduction in the intake of halogen drugs and injections for close monitoring and assessment. For positive results may be the creating and generating of a new healthy mentally stable person worth

impacting the family, community, country and generation positively. This is because, by close monitoring of those who leave the mental facility to the homes are usually seen in a perfect shape, in mood, attitude and behaviour to the admiration of family members, nurses and all. This is a sounding bell worthy of hearing and listening by all stakeholders involved in the healing process of the mentally challenged individual or person.

4.1.4 Other workers around mentally challenged Individual and their impacts

Not only the patient himself/herself or the health worker plays major role in the wellbeing or good mental state attainment. Other personalities apart from the two groups plays all kinds of roles in the healing process of the mentally challenged individual. The group comprises of family members, community opinion leaders, religious leaders, the security services, good Samaritan, citizens, close friends etc. All these people plays all kinds of roles to the positive healing and impacts of the mentally challenged person within the community or society. Such people contribute marginally to the good will and welfare of creating a better future and world for the mentally challenged individual. Some of the ways of contributing includes but not limited to be through money, food, gifts, advice, guidance and counselling, visitations, trainings. All these encouragement are toward a better person and bright future attainment. Final attained life is all about recovery, given of new life and professions of various kinds in the life of the mentally challenged individual. All these people make up the community so that power to make/turn the mentally ill person (excluding genetically generated or obtained mental patients) into a new person that will beneficial to all lies in the hands of the community or society. And the ability to kill the soul through stigmatization and infringing on the rights and principles of the mentally challenged individual also exists.

4.2 Negative impacts from the experiential psychiatrist professionals, cohorts and patients

4.2.1 Recovery Rate

Recovery rate of mentally challenged individual in mental homes or facility is time bound to an extent. As most critical situations observed during the research and field investigations gave positive and negative results. A maximum of two weeks that was observed as facility stationing period for data collection had mentally challenged individuals exposed to the mental health facility coming in for healing and going out smiling when in a better state after a month and beyond. But recovery rate in the long run does have negative impacts or effects as final judgment in some cases. Results are seen in terms of no coordination between sense organs, shaking of hands and legs, madness, crippling and even final death. This is usually not recorded in the individual mental homes or facilities but rather in the mentally ill person homes or houses. This is mostly as a result of the continuous use of mentally challenged or ill drugs for healing on the human mind and brain. The drug abuse or substance abuse individuals also have this same repercussion when they use drugs in unmeasurable quantified amount. I therefore recommend to psychiatrist to take into

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consideration the continuous use of mental or brain enhancement drugs which have both positive and negative effects on the human mind recovery rate since all drugs have a negative impacts on oneself. This is justified by resultant recovery rate when plotted against time of manifestation of mental issue or problem. Some mental observed symptoms and problems have taken over 40 years with the possibility of taken the patient to old age. The symptoms listed above can take the person up to old age to start showing total disaster or negative impacts of the drugs or manifestation to the disadvantage of the individual mentally challenged person.

4.2.2 Negative impacts of experiential patients

Mentally ill patients need to play major critical role towards attaining mental health states in the society. Stigmatization and infringing on the rights of the mentally challenged individuals is very annoying and insulting hence the need to play critical attention, follow all procedures and pay all tributes towards good health and mental wellbeing. Mentally challenged status attainment from any of the processes as according to Danquah (2023) can result in madness or death. Hence the need to work assiduously with all seriousness and alertness to regain your health or the associated wellbeing generated from the realm as you embarks on the journey of psychiatric treatment. The patient should be able to tell the psychiatric doctor which of the drugs is a brain enhancer or constraint and hence applicable to his treatment and wellbeing based on experiences with the drug. As a drug applicable to Mr A will not be applicable to Mr B. To me as a researcher, I think too much drug is addiction as known by all with all kinds of associated repercussions on oneself whether long or short term. The patient should hence be willing to tell the doctor or physician and he/she as a medical expert should also be willing to listen and act accordingly. Acting accordingly means every decision should be in favor of the patient towards healing and normalization. The principal aim in every health facility recovery program has the patient or ill person as the first hand person being worked on. In all these, one ought to know that everyone and his motive and hence the resultant vision, mission, aims and objectives in the institution of work. While someone or institution may be unto good healthy wellbeing attainment and salvation (SDG 3), another may be unto destruction and death.

4.2.3 Experiential Psychiatrist Impacts

The psychiatrist is the first point of call in throwing a mentally challenged person off board into death or helping salvage the situation to give a life. This can be done through drug prescription and dosage application. But once hospitals and mental facilities exist to sort for the wellbeing of a patient or mentally challenged person, the sustainable development goal 3 (SDG 3) ought to stand and worked on. The psychiatric doctor should therefore be fair in diagnosing, prescribing, and in the treatment of mentally challenged individual towards normalization. Even though some cases of mentally challenged status have been diagnosed and worked on, others have not, as some are always in a creating process and making of new things on daily basis. COVID – 19 is an example in this direction as I believe some even

ended up in mental homes after the drastic negative impact on life and livelihoods worldwide. Great and complex ailments and diseases requires great psychiatric thinkers and physicians when it comes to diagnosis, prescription and treatment. In some cases, the drug to prescribe after diagnosis may be a problem and hence a requirement for usage of a drug of similar characteristics, signs, symptoms and healing power. If the psychiatric doctor, nurse or health professional fails in all the treatment process, then the patient is meant unto madness or death. If not then the patient may have to go through serious work, torture, pain and learning to justify for reasons and essence to be alive on earth.

4.2.4 Other workers around mentally challenged Individual and their impacts towards healing

A group comprising of community opinion leaders, religious leaders, security forces, social workers, families, friends, citizens surely makes up the people of the community in addition to the two classes discussed above. So if such a group decides to generate all kinds of negative or social vices or effects on a mentally challenged person. Then that mentally challenged person is meant for death. No one will accept him/her in the community or society. So in a way, members of the community other than the health workers, contributes to the healing, wellbeing and making or unmaking of a mentally challenged person in the community. So if various scenarios are generated to buttress the unimportance and sickness regime of a mentally challenged person, then the person is meant for doom. That is unto death or complete madness. Such generation of mentally retarded or challenged person can easily be done to perceive that the person is sick. This can easily kill the person dreams, aspirations and destiny and hence his ability to achieve great success in life. This is the case and scenario the investigator finds himself during this research and investigation for over a decade. This is same for a lot of people who likely found themselves in the same spot or situation. This is worth further probing and investigation for assessments since it's an issue of global standard and justification for the resultant impacts on man and possible discontinuity of some habits associated with mentally challenged treatment and healings. All members of the society have the ability and strength to help the healing process. Treasure hunters, spiritual and Occultic initiators have this path and key toward wealth generation and resultant mental patient generation in the family and society in Ghana and if possible in Africa and worldwide. It is therefore worth noting that with such people and easy to get rich people, the mentally challenged individual is of no use and or no worth to such easy rich go getters. The main motive of such individuals is get access to the wealth or the treasure and let's make use of it. Such creation is unto destruction. So the life in the process is worth losing and generating and obtaining the needed wealth or huge quantum of treasure is the ultimate aim. So if all the people involved are of this motive; let's get the wealth and money, then the life which is worth protecting will be lost by hook or crook. At this point, it calls on the mentally challenged person to fight for his/her life to the fullest for the salvation of his life and soul. But fighting becomes very difficult if no one is on his side to back him on certain issues or the treatment journey or fighting process for life.

5 CONCLUSION

Experiential inputs by both psychiatric professionals and patients is very important towards determining and generating a healthy being after assiduous works on a mentally challenged individual. This is usually done together with people of the society. Recovering from a mentally challenged world to a healthy world of individuals should be done on the basis of stakeholder participation. It is either achieved in the positive direction or in the negative direction. The positive direction is towards obtaining a healthy wellbeing willing to impact on the family, community, country or world positively. The negative impacts is towards shaking of hands and legs, crippling, madness or completely unto death. In all these scenarios, the experiential workers and patients have to play effective roles towards attainment of needed outputs of final healing.

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